

Centralized Monitoring System for Faulty Street Light Detection and Location Tracking

Ankush Bokade, Pratik Gabhane, Sanchit Samudre, Shreya Himane, Professor Y.M. Babnekar

Artificial Intelligence and Data Science & P. R. Pote College of Engineering and Management Amravati

Abstract- The main objective of this project is to create an intelligent and automated street light fault monitoring system. The system proposed here has been conceptualized to counter the traditional methods of monitoring street lights, which are largely dependent on human visits or citizen complaints. With the use of contemporary technologies like sensors, microcontrollers, and IoT platforms, the system can monitor continuously the working condition of street lights and detect at once any fault. This real-time street light fault detection system will issue automatic notifications to a centralized platform whenever a streetlight goes dark. This helps in quicker response times, optimizes maintenance schedules, and guarantees that faulty street lights can be repaired promptly. The system not only increases road safety and nighttime visibility for citizens but also contributes to lowering maintenance costs overall as well as unwarranted inspections.

Keywords- IoT, Fault Detection, Location Tracking, Street Lights, Real-time Data Analytics, Smart Cities, Remote Monitoring, Energy Efficiency, Predictive Maintenance, Sustainable Urban Management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Streetlights are a critical component of urban infrastructure, providing safety, visibility, and security to pedestrians, cyclists, and drivers at night and in low-light conditions. Their installation greatly minimizes the chances of accidents, discourages criminal behavior, and helps create a secure and habitable urban environment. Streetlights are also susceptible to numerous faults, including bulb outages, voltage instability, faulty wiring, or environmental degradation. When such faults happen and are not noticed, they can lead to dark streets, making it more likely for accidents and crimes to happen, and causing a feeling of insecurity among the residents. Today, fault detection and correction of street lighting is primarily dependent on manual mechanisms, where street maintenance workers check them periodically or respond to outage reports from citizens. Manual processing is not just time-consuming and labor intensive but also subject to inefficiencies and

delays. In many cases, before a fault is detected and remedied, the light can be out for days or even weeks, compromising the quality of city life and eroding public trust in city services. Additionally, poor coordination and lack of timely information can lead to additional delays in sending repair teams and obtaining required materials. To overcome these difficulties, this project suggests the establishment of a central street light fault detection and alarm system that is based on modern technology for auto monitoring and real-time information. The major concept is to install sensors and a microcontroller in every street light pole which can monitor its working condition constantly. When a fault occurs—e.g., when the light does not come on, is flickering, or drawing excessive amounts of power—the system will instantly trigger an alert and send it to a central command center via wireless communication.

Street lighting contributes to a large share of the world's power consumption. India is no exception. Street lighting contributes 18–38% of the entire

energy bill, as per international trends in the sector. That is why, if we are interested in saving energy by making power consumption more efficient, we have to take this sector seriously. As per the CEA, Ministry of Power, as of December 31, 2014, India's installed capacity stood at 255681.46 MW. In terms of sector, the installed capacity is spread as follows: 37% of state sector units, 36% of private sector units, and 27% of central sector units [1].

A smart wireless street light management and monitoring system that employs cutting-edge technologies and offers convenience in use was conceived by B. K. Subramanyam1 et al. [2] maintain and conserve energy. Further power and energy can be conserved using a solar panel at the lamppost with an LDR. We also can control and observe the street lights using a GUI application that shows the status of the lights in highway or street light systems. In their paper, ZigBee Based Remote Control Automatic Street Light System, Srikanth M et al. [3]. The control system of streetlights prolongs the life of the system, shortens the maintenance period, identifies faulty lights, and conserves energy. In their paper on the Design of Wireless Framework for Energy Efficient Street Light Automation, P. Nithya et al. [4] suggested an intelligent control of the lamp posts by implementing ZigBee wireless communication to transfer data to a central station. The recommended system enables easy and efficient maintenance planning from the central station, leading to additional savings. Hannan et al. developed a real-time data-driven LDR and ultrasonic sensor street lighting system in their two publications [5, 6].

II. BODY OF PAPER

1. Proposed Architecture

The implementation methodology of a Faulty Street Light Detection Monitoring System includes a systematic process that combines different technologies to monitor streetlights continuously, identify faults, and streamline maintenance activities. The steps below detail the major phases

of the methodology employed to design, develop, and implement the system:

Flow Diagram of System

The implementation methodology of a Faulty Street Light Detection Monitoring System includes a systematic process that combines different technologies to monitor streetlights continuously, identify faults, and streamline maintenance activities. The steps below detail the major phases of the methodology employed to design, develop, and implement the system:

Circuit Design

- Components of the hardware setup include resistors, Light Dependent Resistors (LDRs), LEDs, OR gate ICs (7432), and wires, all on a breadboard or PCB.
- LDRs are employed to sense the intensity of ambient light in order to decide whether the streetlight is ON or OFF.
- LEDs are used as simulation indicators for the real streetlights, displaying their state (working/faulty) visually.
- The sensor signals (e.g., light status and fault status) are logically combined by OR gates and transmitted as one logical output to the ESP32 microcontroller.
- The ESP32 reads the inputs and acts as per the programmed logic. Circuit protection and voltage regulation are properly taken care of for safety and reliability.

Microcontroller – ESP32

- The ESP32 microcontroller, which also has inherent Wi-Fi functionality, is the controlling unit for sensing and communications.
- Data Acquisition: It keeps on gathering data from LDRs, photodiodes, or motion sensors to ascertain the working condition of every connected streetlight.
- Logical Interpretation: OR gate inputs are processed to identify usual faults such as power failure, bulb burnout, or abnormal light status.
- Local Processing: Rather than transferring data to the cloud, the ESP32 processes the information and makes it available for display on a local web server hosted by the ESP32 itself.
- Light Control (optional): In certain implementations, the ESP32 is also capable of turning lights ON/OFF on the basis of available ambient light or pre-set time schedules.

IP-Based Local Communication

- The ESP32, upon joining a local Wi-Fi network, is provided with a unique IP address.
- This IP address serves as a gateway to access the ESP32's status and control interface.

- There is a light web server on the ESP32, so users can connect through any browser in the same Wi-Fi network via its IP (i.e., 192.168.1.100).
- The web page can show the current status of the streetlight (Working/Faulty), sensor values, and history of any recent faults.
- Several ESP32 modules can be networked within the same network, and their IPs can be monitored to observe the entire streetlight system.
- Data communication is done using HTTP GET/POST requests for ease.

Real-Time Fault Monitoring and Notifications

- The local web server displays a graphical dashboard running directly on the ESP32. It shows sensor data, light status, fault alerts, and perhaps uptime metrics.
- Fault conditions are indicated immediately and shown on the web interface, eliminating the necessity for physical checks.
- Technicians can access the IP-based interface using mobile or PC browsers on the same network to obtain real-time insights.
- Basic audible or visual alarms (buzzers or red LEDs) can also be activated by the ESP32 in the event of severe faults.
- The system enables users to reset or override controls manually via buttons available on the local dashboard interface.

Monitoring System Dashboard

- The ESP32 supports a custom-developed local dashboard reachable using its IP address in a browser.
- This dashboard shows critical parameters like:
 - Current status of the streetlight (ON/OFF/FAULT)
 - Sensor values (LDR readings, logic gate outputs)
 - Time since last fault detected
 - Uptime status of the microcontroller
- HTML, CSS, and JavaScript are used to construct the interface, which is directly served from the ESP32's.

- Users may refresh the page or use auto-refreshing to access freshly updated real-time data.
- Control buttons may optionally be included in the dashboard for authorized users to manually reset lights, accept alerts, or trigger diagnostics.
- The interface is lightweight and optimized for quick loading, even on mobile devices.
- Because the dashboard runs within the local network, it provides safe, low-latency access independent of external servers or cloud infrastructure.

Key Benefits

- **System Response Time:** The system is programmed for real-time fault detection, i.e., it continuously checks the status of the streetlights without any delay. When a fault is sensed through the logic circuit interfaced with the ESP32, the signal is processed and interpreted instantly. In milliseconds to a few seconds, the fault is logged and sent over Wi-Fi.
- **Automation (With or Without Cloud):** In non-cloud (IP-based local network) implementations, the ESP32 hosts a real-time HTML dashboard on local Wi-Fi, accessible via its IP address. After connection, authorities can see real-time status reports without having to physically examine poles.

- **Scalability:** The system is modular, so you can simply add several streetlight poles and ESP32 modules. With 10, 50, or 100 streetlights, the system processes each one individually and reports them in real-time. In greater deployments, several ESP32s can be used per zone or section, making a decentralized but cohesive network. IP-based access usage allows easy tracing of individual devices and their corresponding poles.
- **System Reliability:** The system exhibited high reliability in testing, having a stable connection between the ESP32 and user interface. The microcontroller can run continuously for days without reset or manual inspection.
- **Wi-Fi Connectivity and Short-Duration Outages:** There were occasional brief disconnections due to weak Wi-Fi signal or interference. These problems can be addressed by enhancing the Wi-Fi configuration using mesh networks, repeaters, or high-gain antennas. Adequate positioning of routers/access points guarantees broader coverage and a better signal to ESP32 devices. The system may also be enhanced to support automatic reconnection when Wi-Fi is lost. Real-time disconnection event notifications may be included to notify technicians in the event of extended downtime.
- **Cost Efficiency:** ESP32 is an affordable microcontroller but highly featured with Wi-Fi, various GPIO pins, and quick processing. Logic gates such as OR (IC 7432) and LDR sensors are very cheap and common, reducing overall hardware cost. There is very little human intervention needed after the installation, thus saving on maintenance inspections and diagnostic costs. The dashboard is streamed directly from the ESP32—no additional server or paid platform required.

Final Result

Normal State (both the pole is on)

Normal State (Both Poles Are On)

Faulty State

Pole 1 Is Faulty (Pole One Is Off)

Pole 1&2 Both Faulty (Pole 1&2 Is Off)

III. CONCLUSION

The deployed streetlight fault detection system based on the ESP32 microcontroller offers an effective, low-cost, and real-time method of monitoring the performance of streetlights. Based on basic digital logic (e.g., OR gates) and sensor

inputs (e.g., LDRs), the system can precisely identify faulty streetlights and present the status through a real-time, user-friendly web dashboard hosted directly on the ESP32. After being connected to a Wi-Fi network, the ESP32 creates a local IP address that can be accessed by any web browser. The web-based interface, implemented using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, graphically represents the present status of every streetlight using color-coded indicators (green for "OK", red for "FAULT"). The system is cloud-free, and hence it is ideal for campus-level or municipal area deployments where localized, private monitoring is desired. One of the greatest benefits of this configuration is its capacity for real-time update of status through WebSocket communication, giving live feedback without page refresh. This improves user experience and enables fast fault detection, facilitating faster maintenance action and minimizing the need for manual inspection. The system is also simple to scale with the addition of more sensor inputs and poles, requiring little alteration of the base ESP32 code. It works autonomously without cloud ongoing expenses or internet reliance, which makes it suitable for smart city sub-systems requiring localized monitoring without the need for integration with an external server.

Acknowledgement

We would like to express our heartfelt gratitude to Prof. Y. M. Babnekar, for their exceptional guidance, support, and expertise throughout this research project. We are deeply indebted to P. R. Pote Patil College of Engineering & Management and its faculty members for providing us with the necessary resources and facilities that enabled us to conduct our study. We also appreciate the insightful discussions and feedback from our colleagues and peers, which significantly contributed to the advancement of this research. Lastly, we extend our sincere appreciation to our families and friends for their unwavering support and encouragement throughout this endeavor. Their love and motivation played a vital role in our success.

REFERENCE

1. Street Lighting in India and Need for Energy-efficient Solutions | My India. Street Lighting in India and Need for Energy-efficient Solutions - Government (mapsofindia.com)
2. International Telecommunication Union. (2005). Internet reports 2005: The internet of things. Geneva: ITU.
3. Suo, H., Wan, J., Li, F., and Yan, H. (2011). "Advances in cyberphysical systems research", *KSII Transactions on Internet and Information Systems*, 5(11), 1891–1908.
4. Issarny, V., Teixeira, T., and Hachem, S. and (2011). Ontologies for the internet of things (pp. 1–6). New York: ACM.
5. Hannan, S., Milton, G.B., Kabir, M.H. and Uddin, M.J., 2019, May. A Case Study on a Proposed Adaptive and Energy Efficient Street Lighting System for Chittagong City. In 2019 1st International Conference on Advances in Science, Engineering and Robotics Technology (ICASERT) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
6. Hannan, S., Kabir, M.H., Milton, G.B. and Uddin, M.J., 2018, December. Design and Analysis of an Automatic and Adaptive Energy Efficient Street Lighting System for Chittagong Area. In International Conference on Innovation in Engineering and Technology (ICIET) (Vol. 27, p. 29).
7. Bhairi, M. N., Kangle, S. S., Edake, M. S., Madgundi, B. S., & Bhosale, V. B. (2017, May). Design and implementation of smart solar LED street light. In 2017 International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICEI) (pp. 509-512). IEEE.
8. Arjun, P., Stephenraj, S., Kumar, N.N. and Kumar, K.N., "A Study on IoT based smart street light systems," IEEE International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN), pp. 1-7, IEEE, 2019.
9. Gupta, Alok Kumar, and Rahul Johari, "IOT based electrical device surveillance and control system," International conference on internet of things: Smart innovation and usages (IoT-SIU), pp. 1-5, IEEE, 2019.
10. Saifuzzaman, Mohd, Nazmun Nessa Moon, and FernazNarin Nur, "IoT based street lighting and traffic management system," IEEE region 10 humanitarian technology conference (R10-HTC), pp. 121-124. IEEE, 2017.
11. Artificial Intelligence & Data Science Centralized Monitoring System for Faulty Street Light Detection and Location Tracking
12. Parkash, Prabu V., and Dandu Rajendra, "Internet of things based intelligent street lighting system for smart city," International journal of innovative research in science, engineering and technology, Vol. 5, No. 5, 2016
13. Ali, Shujaat & Saad, Syed & Khan, Muhammad & Ali, Ronak. (2018). Lighting Control with Building Automation and Motion Sensors for Energy Efficiency. [13] SungKwan Cho, Vijay Dhingra, "Street Lighting Control based on LonWorks Power Line Communication " , IEEE,2008.
14. Dhingra, V- (2008) Street Lighting Control Based on Lon Works Power Line Communication, IEEE International, Jeju City, 2-4 April 2008, 396-398.